

HDRC Doncaster Impact Report

Evidence Enriched Place, Building Trust, Co-Creation and Research Capacity

2026

NIHR

Health
Determinants
Research
Collaboration

"It has made me appreciate the importance of robust data collection and how this is communicated in a meaningful and useful way to partners."
 Sarah Atkinson, Women's Health

skills
development

leveraged £13.2M funding
into SY ecosystem from
UK funding councils

"I also saw the buy in of senior council officers, which reinforced the value of research in our environment"
 Graduate Management Trainee

research
infrastructure

research capacity
development

23

collaborators worked
with us on more than
one project

getting along side

16 teams
611 unique
collaborators

“A paper is being published, a follow-up piece of research is being planned. The findings from the project will be used to influence local policy and practice response.”
Saima Nazir-Desforges, Public Health Lead

continuity and sustainability

partnerships and linkages

“We both valued and respected each other’s knowledge and expertise, but also created a safe space to challenge our thinking and learn from each other.”

Nicola Milnes, Starting Point Team Manager

“We will also be looking to expand this agenda across a regional and national footing, and HDRC Doncaster’s involvement will be key in driving this.”

Dani Adams, Skills Transformation Manager, City of Doncaster Council

leadership support

dissemination

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Introduction

In Doncaster, a quiet revolution is taking shape. At the heart of it is the National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR) funded Health Determinants Research Collaboration (HDRC), led by practitioner academic Professor Susan Hampshaw within the City of Doncaster Council. This initiative is building a research active local authority where evidence informs everyday decisions on housing, employment, transport, and culture.

Backed by more than £6 million and strong partnerships with the University of Sheffield and Sheffield Hallam University, the team is embedding researchers within the local authority, co-producing studies that matter locally, and trialling rapid evidence reviews to make knowledge usable at pace. The ambition is bold yet practical: blend research with Doncaster's place-based insight to tackle the wider determinants of health and reduce inequalities. Progress is already visible, and while the journey continues, HDRC Doncaster's approach offers a blueprint for creating an evidence rich culture in local government; quietly transforming how decisions are made, and lives are improved. Here we not only set out examples of our impact, but we also identify the key ingredients that we believe have allowed us to flourish.

**£6M
NIHR
funding**

A note from the Director

Every day in Doncaster, decisions taken in our services, partnerships and communities shape the conditions for health. HDRC Doncaster exists to help make those decisions fairer, faster and more grounded in evidence and lived experience. We have been building something deliberately practical: trusted relationships, shared methods, and the skills to use research where it matters, inside real services and real lives.

We start with trust. Through our Public Involvement and Community Engagement (PICE) “network of networks”, we bring together colleagues from the Council, the VCS, communities and universities so that priorities are co-owned and benefits are shared. This approach has helped us take research to people and with people, from women’s health and youth vaping to inclusive participation in clinical research, so that insight is generated with those most affected and translated quickly into action.

We are also shaping an evidence-informed culture. That means pairing data with lived experience and building governance and tools that make evidence ready at the speed of policy. You will see examples in these pages: from briefing decision makers on complex harms to turning large volumes of resident feedback into usable intelligence; from linked, ethically governed datasets to practical evaluation designs that teams can use to support decision making.

Capability is the engine of all of this. Our research capacity and development work, embedded researchers, practitioner training, internships and academic partnerships, has grown confidence and skills across the system. Practitioners are co-authoring studies, shaping ethical and data processes, and using research methods to focus improvement where it will make the biggest difference.

Finally, we pay close attention to adoption and spread. We package what works: toolkits, templates, dashboards, and move skills through placements, colocation and communities of practice. In this way, approaches tested in Doncaster travel across services locally and into regional and national networks, strengthening practice beyond our own footprint.

This report showcases that journey: trust first, evidence in the room, capability built through doing, and practical diffusion so good ideas don't stay in one place. I'd like to thank everyone, local people, policy makers, practitioners, analysts and academics, who have made this possible. I hope what follows feels usable in your day-to-day work, and I invite you to join the next steps with us.

Professor Susan Hampshaw

Director, HDRC Doncaster

Network of Networks Approach to PICE

Putting inclusion at the centre

HDRC Doncaster starts with architecture that makes inclusion practical at Place, bringing together public health, Rotherham Doncaster and South Humber NHS Foundation Trust (RDaSH), Doncaster and Bassetlaw Teaching Hospitals (DBTH), the Voluntary and Community Sector (VCS), community groups and HDRC Doncaster so that research priorities, ways of working and benefits are co-owned and co-governed. Those most impacted by issues are included in the research: this is justice, fairness and advocacy in practice. HDRC Doncaster ensures we build trusted relationships first, share power in decision making, agree approaches to data and ethics that feel safe to communities and grow capacity across the system, so communities help shape, do and use research.

Starting with Trust

Building relationships through the PICE Steering Group

Trust is built through consistent practice. HDRC Doncaster convenes the PICE Steering Group which is the forum where relationships are formed and maintained at Place, including RDaSH, DBTH, the VCS and community groups, so people can plan, test and learn together. It provides shared governance for inclusive engagement with particular focus on underserved groups (not typically involved in research) and connects multiple networks into a wider fabric of trust, practice and research capacity.

From this platform, HDRC Doncaster have convened and supported workshops and conferences that are genuinely coproduced with communities and partners. Event planning has been retooled into a step-by-step, shareable approach; community partners codesign activities, facilitate sessions and capture data themselves; and colleagues have strengthened links with universities and local employers to widen reach and representation. We have used the Steering Group both to steer activity and to agree practical enablers that make inclusion work at Place. A concrete example is our participant remuneration policy, developed by HDRC Doncaster, sense checked by Steering Group members, and shared with organisations who did not previously have such a policy so they could adapt and use it. This has helped standardise fair recognition of time and expertise across partners.

Putting inclusion at the centre

From Platform to Practice

As one illustration of “community centred trust,” the [Muslim Wellness Conference](#) was co-created with community leaders from the outset and has evolved through doing, testing, learning and adjusting, to provide a safe culturally grounded space for open, non-judgemental conversations about mental health and suicide prevention. An HDRC Doncaster embedded researcher worked alongside the community to build the relationships and infrastructure that enabled community ownership, with workshops forming one component of a day led largely by lived-experience voices.

In addition, HDRC Doncaster (as convenor and secretariat) worked through the PICE Steering Group to plan and shape the 2024 PICE Conference, and then brought partners back together to debrief and agree our future direction of travel for research priority setting.

With this platform of trust in place, the next move is simple: take research to people and with people, starting where interest and need are highest.

“As someone personally affected by suicide, I know how silenced these experiences can feel within the intersections of culture, faith and community, where fear of judgement often prevents people from speaking openly. This is why creating safe, culturally grounded spaces for honest conversations about trauma, stress, depression and suicide matters so deeply. The Muslim Wellness Conference achieved exactly that and would not have been possible over the past two years without that partnership”

Akeela Mohammed, Director Healthy Her and Chair of Inclusion & Fairness Forum

18

number of teams worked with on PICE related research projects

Taking Research to People

Women's Health as a system-wide, inclusive effort

HDRC Doncaster's approach to "taking research to people" is exemplified by the Women's Health Initiative. Prompted by the national Women's Health Strategy, the Women's Health Initiative brought together public health practitioners, an HDRC Doncaster embedded researcher, council teams and the Voluntary and Community Sector to consolidate previously fragmented data into an accessible overview. This [evidence base](#) identified priority areas to tackle inequalities and revealed critical data gaps, especially the lack of sex- and intersection-disaggregated information on women and girls facing multiple disadvantage, balancing the need to act fast with the insight needed for sustained progress.

Taking research to people and with people saw around 70 people convened including stakeholders from health, the local authority and the VCS to discuss findings and co-develop next steps. This power of convening sparked new collaborations and allowed a HDRC Doncaster embedded researcher to spot fundable research questions, including an application to an NIHR development award focused on menstrual health and period poverty co-developed with a range of local partners.

A follow up workshop was held in November 2025 attended by approximately 80 stakeholders to continue developing plans to support the health and wellbeing of women and girls in Doncaster. Themed discussions facilitated by local lead professionals and the Women and Girls' Health Initiative team, are leading to specific local actions with a shared commitment to driving health and wellbeing improvement.

From insights to commissioning: Insights from the women's health evidence synthesis and partner workshops have been used to inform the commissioning process for sexual and reproductive health services. Updates and insights from the initiative have been shared through input to the Health and Wellbeing Board to inform local priorities and mobilise strategic support. The work is also shaping local commissioning: in early discussions, the Director of Public Health, Rachael Leslie, highlighted that the Women's Health Strategy and the Local Contraceptive Aspirations survey are "already informing commissioning priorities for sexual and reproductive health services and shaping the direction of travel for future service design, ensuring alignment with identified needs and the Borough Strategy ambitions and equity and prevention."

[Open access outputs](#) provide 'ready to use' [resources](#) for communities, practitioners and commissioners. By convening public health practice, the VCS and HDRC Doncaster around women's health, we have built a living network of trust, practice and capacity, valuing lived experience alongside data and moving evidence into conversations, workshops and decisions across Doncaster.

“The level of planning was clear for all to see and the energy in the room was electric, demonstrating how invested people are in improving women’s health... there is definitely a positive energy growing around this work and we have excellent engagement from wider partners.”

Mandy Espey, Health Inequalities Lead Doncaster Place

HDRC Doncaster use the same mechanism of taking research to people and with people to tackle inclusion in clinical research. The Skin Perfusion project shows how meeting communities where they are changes participation.

Meeting Communities Where They Are

This project around removing skin bias in medical devices confronted a challenge that is often overlooked in clinical research: how to make participation genuinely inclusive. At its core, the study aimed to test the feasibility and performance of a device for patients with chronic limb threatening ischemia undergoing endovascular revascularisation. Before recruitment could begin, the team asked a critical question: ‘Who gets left out of trials like these and why?’ HDRC Doncaster worked alongside the research team to establish inclusive early focus groups, engaging members of the local Chinese community, a local Muslim ladies’ group (Healthy Her) and a local African Caribbean group – all historically underrepresented in clinical studies.

HDRC Doncaster facilitated conversations that enabled settings for all focus groups to be decided by individual communities, with the Muslim ladies and African Caribbean communities taking place at their regular meeting spots. This rebalanced the power dynamics between the communities and the research team and allowed people the comfort and confidence to speak openly and freely.

These conversations revealed practical and cultural barriers that shape participation:

- Language gaps that make consent forms and trial information inaccessible.
- Limited awareness of what clinical research involves and why it matters.
- Trust issues, rooted in unfamiliarity with research processes and concerns about safety.

Insights revealed steps to improve awareness and participation, including:

- Culturally tailored communication, using plain language and translated materials.
- Community led promotion, where trusted local voices—not researchers—introduce the study.
- Suggestions for venues and timing that fit community routines, reducing logistical barriers.

This work connects to HDRC Doncaster’s wider network of networks model, which brings together community organisations, academic partners and health innovators. By linking local insights to regional and national infrastructure, such as Health Innovation Yorkshire & Humber, the NIHR MedTech Cooperative in Surgical Technologies and the NIHR BRC Methodology Hub, we are creating a pipeline where equity is designed in from the start. Together these networks create the conditions for an evidence-enriched culture across Doncaster.

Evidence Informed Culture

Building on strong community partnerships, the next step is embedding evidence into governance and policy so that decisions reflect both data and lived experience. This section demonstrates how research and the embedded researcher become a catalyst for systemic change, influencing strategic planning and regulation. Through examples like the Fairness and Wellbeing Commission, and public health interventions, HDRC Doncaster demonstrate how evidence can drive coordinated, forward looking approaches.

From Insight to Influence

The Fairness and Wellbeing Commission was set up to answer a pressing question: ‘What does fairness look like in Doncaster, and how do we get there?’ The Commission operated like an evidence review board using participatory workshopping methodologies, with HDRC Doncaster embedded researchers working alongside commission members to gather evidence from multiple sources; systematic reviews, local data, and lived experience, to build a clearer picture of inequality and its impact on health and wellbeing. The findings were sobering. Around 129,000 residents live in areas among the most deprived in England. More than 21,000 children grow up in poverty, and 27,000 working adults earn less than the real living wage. Healthy life expectancy is just 57 years for men and 56 years for women, with gaps of up to 8 years between the most and least deprived communities. These figures underline why urgent action is required. HDRC Doncaster embedded researchers suggested an inverted stages of life model for presentation of evidence – progressing from older people to children and young people. Within this framework they presented examples of interventions alongside current practice initiatives from elsewhere in the UK.

23

Number of organisations involved in Fairness and Wellbeing Commission

worked alongside

41

members of the Fairness and Wellbeing Commission

Supported by HDRC Doncaster’s embedded researchers, the Commission produced a [final report](#) including [16 evidence based recommendations and 4 enablers for change](#), focusing on supporting young people, tackling in-work poverty, and ensuring equitable access to services. These recommendations are now informing local strategies and shaping conversations across the City of Doncaster Council.

HDRC Doncaster helped make this work distinctive through methodological innovation including [Logic models](#) which mapped cause and effect relationships, ethnographic research captured the realities of life in deprived communities, and [personas](#) helped decision makers see data through human stories. This approach did not just generate a report, it created a shared understanding and strengthened partnerships between local government, universities, and community organisations.

With HDRC Doncaster’s support for knowledge mobilisation, the Commission hosted a dedicated session in March 2024 to review early impacts and align partners on next steps. This collaborative process has left Doncaster with more than recommendations, it has provided a repeatable model for evidence informed governance, blending academic rigor with local insight and co-design.

Downloads of our training resources

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Evidence at the Speed of Policy

While the Fairness and Wellbeing Commission provided a long-term framework for tackling inequality, HDRC Doncaster also supports rapid responses when evidence needs to be mobilised quickly. The next example shows how HDRC Doncaster supported rapid evidence mobilisation to target open policy windows. When Doncaster faced a gambling license application, the question was not just regulatory, it was about safeguarding communities already vulnerable to harm. HDRC Doncaster’s Gambling Harms project provided a timely solution: an [evidence briefing](#) and a risk map that combined global research, national policy insights, and local data on gambling premises and population risk factors. This wasn’t a theoretical exercise, it was a practical tool designed for decision makers.

The briefing was used to [object to a license application](#), demonstrating how evidence can influence outcomes when it’s ready at the right moment.

Public health teams worked alongside HDRC Doncaster’s embedded researchers to learn how to synthesise evidence streams, critically appraise interventions, and translate findings into policy ready formats. Feedback from practitioners described the process as “constructive and confidence-building”.

Working alongside the Healthy Places team, the project also introduced visual tools, such as mapping licensed premises against demographic vulnerability, making complex evidence accessible for non-specialists. These innovations helped colleagues across the council see the bigger picture and strengthened the case for action.

What is emerging is an HDRC Doncaster replicable model for other public health challenges, fast, rigorous, and practical. It combines three elements:

- Timely evidence synthesis tailored to local context
- Embedded researcher support to build skills, research capacity and confidence
- Actionable outputs, briefings and maps, that can be deployed in real-world decisions

HDRC Doncaster is now informing conversations about how Doncaster can respond to other determinants of health, from alcohol licensing to advertising restrictions. It is not just about producing evidence; it is about making sure evidence is ready when policy windows open.

“I used the evidence briefing to object to a licence application. It turned a complex public health argument into something our colleagues could act on”

Caroline Temperton, Healthy Places Team Lead

42

Events hosted

Data as a Driver: Building an Evidence-Enriched Place

What changes when a programme treats data as shared infrastructure rather than a back-office tool?

Across HDRC Doncaster supported projects, HDRC Doncaster embedded researchers are changing how the system works, not only producing analysis, but building the culture, capability and governance that make evidence usable. The examples below show partners working as if data is a common good: linked, accessible and ethically governed. This is shifting how problems are understood and solved, with lived experience alongside robust analysis, dashboards replacing static reports, and evaluation designed in from day one.

Ageing Friendly Survey

- From 9,000 free text responses, an HDRC Doncaster embedded researcher used Natural Language Processing and an interactive Power BI dashboard to turn comments into usable insight, allowing officers and Voluntary and Community Sector partners to explore intersectional inequalities and act upon them.

Early Years linkage (governance by design)

- HDRC researcher provided data linkage across maternity, Early Years, and Health Visiting with clear hypotheses and repeatable governance. HDRC Doncaster produced Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIA's) and Data Sharing Agreements (DSA's) so the approach can scale without reinventing processes.

Nourish & Nurture and BaBiD (longitudinal outcomes, low burden).

- HDRC Doncaster led data linking between routine service data and Born and Bred in Doncaster (BaBiD) to reveal long term outcomes without additional burden on families, allowing evaluation to be designed in from the outset.

MAIHDA for the 2–2½ Health Visiting review (precision on inequality).

- An HDRC Doncaster embedded researcher trialed Multilevel Analysis of Individual Heterogeneity and Discriminatory Accuracy (MAIHDA) for the mandated Ages and Stages 2–2½ health visiting review to quantify intersectional differences and target improvement precisely.

City Centre Antisocial Behaviour (evidence into operating rhythm).

- Alongside HDRC Doncaster, the ASB team built a Kellogg style Theory of Change to steer delivery and accountability.

Housing Strategy (fast path from analysis to policy).

- An HDRC Doncaster embedded researcher taught data linkage methods while the policy officer led the analysis, moving evidence quickly into policy discussion.

In practical terms, HDCR Doncaster has prioritised standardised tooling (e.g., Taguette for qualitative analysis) and practical guidance ensure dashboards, maps and briefings are usable without an analyst on hand, enabling the local authority to apply routine, repeatable methods without excessive licence fees. Together these shifts weave linked, analysable data; actionable outputs; inequality sensitive methods; evaluation by design; and shared capability directly into project delivery, credible now and ready to scale as others adopt them.

Why this matters, ingredients of evidence informed project portfolio:

- Linked, analysable data across participating services with proportionate, repeatable governance.
- Actionable, interactive insights (dashboards, maps, briefings) that practitioners can use without an analyst at their elbow.
- Methods that see inequality clearly moving beyond averages to who needs what, where and when.
- Evaluation by design, with Theories of Change (TOCs) influencing practice and longitudinal linkage to see impact over time.
- Shared capability from DPIAs/DSAs to qualitative software- so evidence is safe, ethical and co-owned.

Innovation Starts with Collaboration - Building Research Capacity

Sustaining change takes more than intent; it takes investment in people, skills and shared ownership of research. HDCR Doncaster applies established research capacity development (RCD) frameworks to make evidence part of everyday decision making, not a specialist afterthought. The aim is simple and practical: create conditions where evidence is understood, applied and valued in the day-to-day work that shapes healthier communities.

HDCR Doncaster’s approach rests on three principles. First, research capacity development is a process: it develops people and strengthens institutions by building a research ready workforce through learning by doing, mentoring and clear development pathways, supported by defined roles and training that grow confidence and capability. Second, it is political and dynamic: it recognises the shifting relationships between evidence, policy and practice and invests in the mechanisms that make research useful: collaboration, clear expectations about how research links to service decisions, time and resource, and a shared belief that research is everyone’s business. Third, it is collective: progress depends on three interconnected pillars: people, infrastructure and partnerships, so we couple workforce development with the governance, tools and data sharing systems that make research possible, and with deep collaboration across the local authority, academic partners and VCSE organisations to create co-ownership and impact.

Here we detail three complementary mechanisms in three different projects used by HDCR Doncaster to build research capacity:

- doing research with communities and colleagues
- building cross system capacity and shared understanding
- embedding research inside operational delivery, to turn evidence into action.

“What was really great for me was the opportunity to learn from, develop skills and knowledge in conducting research and to be able to put those into practice... Have really felt a part of the journey and valued to bring my prior knowledge and expertise to this project as well as building research skills.”

Local authority practitioner, City of Doncaster Council (July 2025)

Why This Matters

These projects share a common thread: they empower people to see research as something they can do, not something done to them. By HDRC Doncaster investing in skills, relationships, and shared ownership, we are creating a local ecosystem where evidence informs policy and practice, and where individuals (whether young people, practitioners, or future researchers), feel confident to ask questions, seek answers, and use findings to make change. For HDRC Doncaster, building research capacity is not just about producing knowledge; it is about creating a culture of curiosity and collaboration that will sustain healthier communities for years to come.

Co-Creation with Practitioners – Research as a Mechanism

Having established why building research capacity is essential, the next example shows what this looks like in practice, starting with researchers and practitioners working together to shape meaningful enquiry through doing research. For HDRC Doncaster, research is a practical mechanism to include those most affected, grow skills in the system, and move evidence into real-world decisions.

Our Young People and Vaping project exemplifies this: a [co-created qualitative study exploring how young people understand vaping among their peers](#), designed and delivered by a team comprising local authority practitioners and HDRC Doncaster embedded researchers. Four focus groups with 17 young people (aged 13–23) ran between May and September 2024, with practitioners trained to shape research questions, conduct Public, Patient Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) in research, facilitate groups, analyse data and coauthor outputs.

The study produced clear, actionable recommendations that partners are drawing on to strengthen local responses:

- Tailor information and support to different patterns of vape use, with targeted support where inequalities are greatest.
- Ensure reliable, accessible sources of information and expand trained outreach and engagement to broaden access.
- Tackle the commercial determinants of health, including approaches to illegal trading, alongside harms messaging.

These insights are translating into practice: additional investment in Trading Standards has been made, open, accessible resources based on the findings are being produced, and findings are being shared across practitioner and academic networks to support adoption and spread.

[Further funding was secured from the NIHR School for Public Health Research to extend and develop the study findings.](#) The next phase will focus on embedding youth voice into local authority responses to forthcoming tobacco and vaping legislation and on maintaining ongoing connections with young people to inform practice. HDRC Doncaster have convened colleagues from across the HDRC network to contribute, and two early career embedded researchers are coinvestigators on the award (individual capacity building). In parallel, HDRC Doncaster works with Sheffield Addictions Research Group at the University of Sheffield (SARG), to provide academic advice and input to the South Yorkshire Tobacco Control Alliance (SYTCA) (organisational infrastructure and collaborative relationships), ensuring a theory informed, evidence-based approach to policy across the region.

Why this matters - research as a mechanism

- Research capacity and confidence: HDRC Doncaster built research capacity through practitioner training and co-authorship which turned research from something done to services into something done by and with them.
- Voice and inclusion: Through HDRC Doncaster’s inclusive approach, youth perspectives directly shaped recommendations and next steps, ensuring responses reflect lived experience.
- Policy readiness and spread: Evidence is being used to inform enforcement and preparation for legislative change, and the work has expanded to three local authority sites with academics from four universities, creating a pathway for wider impact.

By treating research as a mechanism, HDRC Doncaster is creating conditions that build skills, centres youth voice and produces actionable insight, we are creating conditions where evidence and advocacy move together, and where local practice can respond quickly and fairly to emerging public health challenges.

Evaluating Services Together: Starting Point

An HDRC Doncaster embedded researcher led the Starting Point service evaluation, demonstrating how research capacity is built by conducting research and evaluation alongside practice. HDRC Doncaster also used this evaluation as an opportunity to train researchers beyond the Starting Point team in qualitative analysis methods, extending capability across the wider system. Local authority practitioners co-produced aims, methods, materials and recommendations, with HDRC Doncaster’s support focused on interpreting results and shaping actionable changes an approach that grows confidence without “taking the work away” from services.

This hands on model helped move a team within Starting Point further along the path from research curious to research active with practitioners reporting new skills and confidence (including a colleague who moved from feeling intimidated by research to collaborating on a [SPHR funded follow on evaluation of the Assessment Hub](#)).

Outputs at a glance

- 70 page [evaluation report](#) with operational, strategic and system level recommendations
- Two sense check workshops to test findings and refine recommendations with service leads
- Two [conference presentations](#).
- [Onward funding](#) to co-develop the Assessment Hub evaluation (health and wellbeing hub in the local homelessness hostel)
- Strengthened partnership between Adult Social Care and HDRC Doncaster to support future projects

The Starting Point Evaluation shows research capacity building through doing, coaching, and shared ownership, fully aligned with HDRC Doncaster’s approach to make research part of everyday decision-making.

The evaluation did not just produce findings, it sparked curiosity. A Policy Insight and Change Officer in homelessness services, supported through ‘*art of the possible*’ sessions with an HDRC embedded researcher, turned their curiosity into a new project: homelessness mapping (see [Seeing the Whole System: Homelessness Mapping for Collective Action](#)).

“We both valued and respected each other’s knowledge and expertise, but also created a safe space to challenge our thinking and learn from each other.”
Nicola Milnes, Starting Point Team Manager

Lead to further funding and new research collaborations

Embedding Research in Practice: Housing Retrofit and Net Zero

Beyond individual development, research capacity building also supports growth at team and organisational levels. Our indoor air quality and health whole house retrofit project shows how embedding research into everyday service delivery helps teams gain confidence, strengthens cross-sector collaboration, and creates structures that make research a tool for learning and a routine part of decision making. This innovative study provides real world insights into the impacts of whole house retrofit on properties, people, and place, helping to shape smarter and more evidence based approaches going forward.

Working alongside teams such as [City of Doncaster Council's Built Environment team](#) and the [University of Sheffield's Department of Civil Engineering as well as School of Architecture, HDRC Doncaster](#) was able to broker relationships that led to trusted collaborations and research capacity building for all.

This led to the introduction of research grade indoor air quality monitors into 21 social houses during whole house retrofit works, supported by £125,000 in external grant funding from the South Yorkshire Sustainability Centre. These trusted relationships and collaborations saw us becoming a named partner on the [EPSRC Engineering Healthier Environment Micro Network AirHub award](#), enabling local authority officers to work alongside academic partners collecting and analysing datasets, as well as damp and mould sampling. This was not just about technical steps; it was about creating opportunities for research capacity and skill development alongside confidence building.

Working alongside HDRC Doncaster, local teams received training in data analysis and interpretation, learned how to navigate ethics applications, and co-developed cross-partnership data management protocols. Academic partners, including early career researchers, conducted real world research beyond their conventional lab settings. Ethics applications and Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) were designed together which led to stronger trusted partnerships. Literature reviews were conducted to inform the Community Engagement Plan, turning what could have been a purely academic exercise into a practical learning experience for practitioners and local authority officers. This shaped a more localised and tailored model for advice, training and support. Taken together, these activities brought health, people, and place explicitly into traditionally physical science research, and helped teams understand how evidence can shape decisions about ventilation, damp prevention, and energy efficiency, critical factors for achieving net zero and targeting measurably improved health outcomes where health inequalities are prevalent.

"In indoor air research it is essential we carry out monitoring to understand real environments, when lived in by real people. We were a team of engineers with expertise in air flows, and particle transport, but no experience of working with homes. The collaboration with HDRC Doncaster has provided us with opportunities to access real spaces, but more importantly the conversations have upskilled our researchers to enable us to do this in a safe and respectful manner, providing us with the confidence to undertake this essential work in the real world."

Dr Abigail Hathway, University of Sheffield, School of Mechanical, Aerospace and Civil Engineering.
January 2026

HDRC Doncaster also created pathways for sustained engagement by using its co-locator model to embed a full-time postdoctoral researcher ([funded through the EPSRC Engineering Healthier Environment Micro Network AirHub Award](#)) within City of Doncaster Council to link local priorities to cutting edge indoor air quality research, ensuring knowledge continues to flow both ways and that research capacity building remains embedded in practice. This embedded role facilitated day-to-day collaboration and provided access to academic and local authority networks alike.

The strength of this collaborative, evidence-led approach has been recognised externally, with the City of Doncaster Council named a finalist for the Retrofit Academy Award for ['Retrofit Local Authority of the Year'](#). The retrofit engagement strategy and the whole house retrofit research were named as contributing factors for being shortlisted alongside Greater Manchester Combined Authority, Bristol City Council and West Midlands Combined Authority.

Seeing the Whole System: Homelessness Mapping for Collective Action

When the Homelessness and Housing Board reorganised, one truth stood out: it was difficult for one single team to see the whole picture. HDRC Doncaster designed and led a series of systems mapping workshops that aimed to get alongside services. This meant joining their rhythms, standing in existing meetings, listening first, and using the language people already work with. From there, partners began to sketch the homelessness system as they experience it day-to-day: how demand arrives, who responds, where decisions get made, and what gets in the way. The scope is practical and focused, acute homelessness, social housing, and supported/temporary accommodation, because teams wanted a map that they could actually use to coordinate effort where it counts most.

External
funding into LA
£162K

HDRC Doncaster’s way of working changes the feel of research. Rather than arriving with a finished framework, the team brings lightweight prompts from the evidence on drivers of homelessness and then co-builds the map with practitioners. Workshops were run as working sessions, not seminars: people cluster around tables, test assumptions, and surface how activities connect across services. Those connections are captured in a Fuzzy Cognitive Map* (*defined below*), a living picture of the system that shows which factors push and pull on outcomes, where feedback loops amplify or dampen effects, and where the system is strong or thin. Between sessions, HDRC Doncaster researchers consolidate the map, check back with participants, and prepare the next step so momentum keeps building. “Getting alongside” also means designing for power and inclusion.

Ground rules and facilitation plans are agreed upfront; community voice is brought to the room as well as in through targeted conversations and validation steps. Because teams cocreate the map, they own the findings: people can point to a loop and say “here’s where a small change could have a big effect.”

To help build sustainable research capacity in systems mapping approaches, HDRC Doncaster worked alongside a Senior Policy & Insight Manager leading the development of the Homelessness Strategy. This partnership went beyond technical delivery: it modelled an approach where research skills are shared and strengthened through joint practice.

Together, they codesigned and facilitated workshops, created maps, and carried out joint analysis, enabling the Manager to build confidence in applying the methodology independently. This collaborative model is intentionally designed so the methodology can be embedded and replicated whenever required, irrespective of service area. This diffusion of systems mapping methodologies has strengthened long-term organisational capability and in turn evidence informed policy and decision making.

What this unlocks in practice

- A shared mental model that helps partners align priorities and coordinate action instead of working in silos.
- A line of sight from insight to change - the feedback loops and gaps make it easier to target opportunities, join up between services, or focused interventions.
- Evidence informed decisions - partners have a shared, rigorous view of system drivers, enabling more confident and transparent choices.
- Spread and sustainability - staff can reuse the HDRC Doncaster model for future strategy work, not just this project.

Mapping for collective action

**Fuzzy Cognitive Map is a soft computing technique used to model complex systems by visualizing causal relationships between concepts using fuzzy logic to represent the strength and direction of connections.*

These projects demonstrate that when research is aligned with local authority service areas and underpinned by structured skill building, it becomes a driver of innovation and confidence. The next step is to adopt and spread this approach, locally, regionally, and nationally.

Adoption & Spread - Training, Skills Bank and the Diffusion Mechanism

Within HDRC Doncaster projects, training works as a diffusion mechanism: skills move with people, methods are packaged into reusable assets, and we have invested in knowledge management processes, so behaviours can take root through colocation and communities of practice. As officers, embedded researchers and students learn together, the work spreads; locally first, then regionally and nationally, so evidence informed approaches show up where decisions are made.

The mechanism in brief

HDRC Doncaster teach, mentor and get alongside → [🔗 HDRC Doncaster package what works](#) (toolkits, dashboard patterns, governance templates) → we sit alongside services (co-location, placements) → we convene peer spaces (communities of practice) → we standardise ethics and data sharing → we track adoption signals (used in policy, commissioning, and service design). It is simple, repeatable, and visible.

A practical illustration of HDRC Doncaster’s diffusion mechanism: we co-hosted training on trauma informed approaches with Sheffield Hallam University, then mentored frontline officers and peer researchers within the Amber Project. The resulting materials and methods were packaged as reusable assets and are now being lifted into other projects and service areas. In addition, creative methods workshops coordinated by HDRC Doncaster colleagues from the University of Sheffield, Sheffield Hallam University and City of Doncaster Council, open to community partners and the VCS, have generated bespoke materials that now sit within our training bank and continue to support wider capacity building.

Local influence (City of Doncaster Council and partners)

HDRC Doncaster's training, mentoring and colocation are making evidence 'everyday' inside services. Theories of Change are used in planning and review; reusable governance patterns (DPIAs and Data Sharing Agreements) are routinely used; and dashboards are embedded in team meetings to support decisions. Embedded research and evaluation feed methods and learning straight back into practice, while a growing research community inside local authority teams shares skills and reflective practice. Briefings and analyses are being used in real policy moments and real time text analysis is giving officers and VCS partners accessible insight on inequalities.

Examples of the local mechanism at play:

- HDRC Doncaster co-host research and evaluation roles embedded in services – Patience Gansallo (Healthy Places team) is leading the [Evaluation of the Active Travel Alliance](#) and contributed to the successful [NIHR PHIRST bid that is now evaluating Health Impact Assessments in Spatial Planning](#) alongside Wakefield City Council. Amy Lazar (Healthy Lives team) is leading food systems research. Both roles are supervised and supported by HDRC Doncaster, ensuring methods, learning and evidence practices are continually fed back into day-to-day team practice.
- Research community inside local authority teams – HDRC Doncaster has created a shared intellectual space for embedded researchers, giving staff in local authority services access to a supportive scholarly community. Colleagues such as Alex Bugg (Insight and Evaluation Lead, Pathways to Work) and Dr Ciara Higham (postdoctoral researcher in indoor air quality).
- Standardised innovative research infrastructure: HDRC Doncaster designed a tripartite Data Sharing Agreement (City of Doncaster Council, Sheffield Hallam University, University of Sheffield) which now references a live 'dynamic data list', (a shared register of the specific datasets/fields being exchanged) so IG teams can update entries per project without reissuing the DSA, creating a repeatable, auditable pathway for projects. Dashboard patterns embedded in meetings – Power BI coordination has strengthened.
- Project tracking and the routine use of dashboards in steering and delivery meetings, enabling clearer decision making and easier, real time review of project progress.
- Evidence into commissioning signals – Women's Health outputs moved into commissioning windows (see section Taking Research to People).
- Rapid policy use of briefings – Gambling Harms evidence briefing and risk map being used to object to a license application, demonstrating policy ready diffusion of HDRC Doncaster methods.
- Data into everyday insight – HDRC Doncaster used and taught real time data analysis methods to draw evidence and insights from over 9,000 free text comments in the Ageing Friendly data and translated into evidence ready, explorable dashboard, giving officers and VCS partners easy, routine access to insights on intersectional inequalities.
- HDRC Doncaster contributed to the [2024 Director of Public Health \(DPH\) Annual Report](#), which highlighted HDRC Doncaster's embedded research and demonstrated its alignment with Doncaster's Health and Wellbeing Strategy 2024–2030. We also contributed to the 2025 DPH Annual Report and supported activities such as storytelling circles.

Regional influence (Yorkshire & Humber)

HDRC Doncaster [methods and assets](#) [travel through joint projects](#), peer learning spaces, and shared governance patterns, so neighbouring authorities can adopt proven approaches without starting from scratch. HDRC Doncaster’s training, communities of practice, and a curated bank of reusable tools enable rapid lift and shift across services. Deliberative initiatives (such as citizen juries) and cross authority evaluations act as practical testbeds that refine methods and make them portable. HDRC Doncaster’s network of networks approach connects research, policy and practice communities, helping teams map connectors and adopters, align priorities, and create repeatable routes for reuse across the region. HDRC Doncaster supporting and enabling external practitioner programmes and awards, further strengthen a pipeline of practitioner researchers who circulate skills between local authorities and academic partners, reinforcing regional capacity over time.

- **Commercial Determinants Citizen Jury** – HDRC Doncaster organised a Yorkshire & Humber citizen jury with Edinburgh University (Prof Jeff Collin), the [SPECTRUM Consortium](#) and our colleagues in HDRC Wakefield, creating a structured space for residents’ voice and multiple authorities to interrogate harms from the proliferation of unhealthy products (specifically unhealthy food, alcohol, and tobacco and vaping). This work supported co-consideration of policy responses, demonstrating Doncaster’s convening influence and positioning it as a regional hub for evidence informed practice.
- **Regional practitioner pipeline** – The other three South Yorkshire local authorities secured NIHR RSS Specialist Centre for Public Health Local Authority Research Practitioners with guidance from HDRC Doncaster, embedding research capacity across the region.
- **Connected policy-engagement networks** - HDRC Doncaster are working with [Y-PERN](#), [YPIP](#) and [UPEN](#), and hosted a pan Yorkshire and Humber ‘Network of Networks’ meeting at City of Doncaster Council. We continue to work across this footprint through the [Yorkshire and Humber Community of Practice for Knowledge Mobilisation](#).
- HDRC Doncaster chairs a Yorkshire and Humber community of practice meeting, which brings together Academic Career Development leads from across the NIHR infrastructure across the region.

Examples of the local mechanism at play:

- **Cross authority evaluation pathway** – Joint successful bid NIHR PHIRST to evaluate Health Impact Assessments in Spatial Planning establishes a cross-regional learning network: we ask questions together, use research methods to unpick those and build shared understanding that informs local actions across sites.

National influence (NIHR pathways and wider networks)

National pathways turn local practice into a [replicable practice](#). Practitioner fellowship and placement schemes create time and structure for staff to deepen methods, circulate skills between organisations, and bring enhanced capability back into services. Cross site collaborations and national working groups act as testbeds that refine approaches and make them portable across contexts. Knowledge mobilisation communities of practice and national events provide routes to showcase methods, surface demand, and enable practical reuse. Standardised governance patterns (ethics and data sharing) and a portable asset library (training, templates, dashboard patterns) support consistent adoption at scale. Recognition loops, through national platforms and publications, reinforce legitimacy and help embed approaches across wider systems.

We highlighted selected examples to illustrate the approach:

- NIHR Academy Awards as a diffusion pipeline** – Carrie Wardle ([recipient of a NIHR predoctoral award](#)), already rooted in HDCRC Doncaster’s work and supported through her doctoral fellowship bid, now undertakes a NIHR Doctoral Awards, with her 20% practice placement within HDCRC Doncaster. [Joanna Rutter](#) (NIHR Doctoral Award, Sheffield City Council) uses her practice time in Doncaster to import and export methods across local authorities. Together, these fellowships strengthen the practitioner–academic route and help build research capacity across the sub-region accelerating learning and spreading HDCRC Doncaster approaches to developing research cultures within local government.
- National influence through STAR** – Doncaster’s youth voice vaping work has scaled into a national research collaboration through the [STAR project](#), which is a collaboration between HDCRC Doncaster, HDCRC Newcastle and HDCRC Tower Hamlets. The project supports local authorities across England to include youth voices in their responses to forthcoming national tobacco and vaping legislation, such as the ban on single use vapes (June 2025) and the smokefree generation policy, demonstrating how HDCRC Doncaster’s co-created methods and insight driven approaches are now shaping national policy preparation and local implementation across multiple regions.
 - Knowledge mobilisation leadership** – Several HDCRC Doncaster investigators, including Professor Liddy Goyder, Professor Andrew Booth and Professor Susan Hampshaw, are coinvestigators on the national [Knowledge for Public Health programme](#). Their involvement provides HDCRC Doncaster with direct learning on how to mobilise knowledge effectively within local government and creates routes for Doncaster’s own evidence informed approaches to influence wider national practice.
 - Publications that travel** - Our peer reviewed publications, conference posters and presentations, package HDCRC Doncaster tested approaches into citable resources that others can adopt, adapt and teach, amplifying spread through co authorship networks and reusable materials.
- Recognition and showcasing** – Doncaster’s [DPH Annual Report \(2024\)](#) featuring HDCRC Doncaster’s practice was highlighted by the Association of Directors of Public Health at the national celebration event and provides a platform to showcase how the embedded research infrastructure plays a role in addressing structural inequalities.
- National award finalists** for City of Doncaster’s Sustainability Unit for the Retrofit Academy Award for [‘Retrofit Local Authority of the Year’](#)- Naming the evidence informed retrofit engagement strategy and the whole house retrofit research project as contributing factors for being shortlisted.

adoption and spread

Collaborators engaged:
136 unique collaborators
across 85 projects
evidencing breadth of
method uptake across
services and partners

Governance reuse: Tri-party
DSA in place and standard
DPIA/DSA templates used
across Early Years, Nourish &
Nurture and other projects.

Dashboard utilisation: Routine use
of Workstreams/Project allocation
dashboards in steering and delivery
meetings (Power BI), with project
distribution and staff allocation
tracked for learning

Policy/commissioning citations:
Retender decision for Adult Sexual
& Reproductive Health Services
linked to Women’s Health evidence;
Gambling Harms briefing deployed
in licensing objection

**Grant pipeline as adoption
proxy:** leveraged £13.2M
funding into SY ecosystem
from UK funding councils
indicating repeated use of
Doncaster tested
approaches in external bids

a diffusion mechanism of research capacity

Internships: Building a Pipeline of Practitioner-Academics

While co-creation empowers practitioners, youth voice and communities, internships create structured pathways for future practitioner-academics and embedding mentorship into everyday practice. For HDRC Doncaster Internships are a deliberate diffusion mechanism: structured placements match skilled interns with live local authority projects, co-supervision by practitioners and academics embeds learning in everyday service work and the outputs are reused across teams. This builds capability now, grows a future workforce of practitioner-academics, and strengthens Doncaster’s skills and training bank.

Internships operate as an in-practice learning lab: a small, codesigned bank of ready to go mini projects allows interns to start fast on work that aligns with service priorities in locally relevant projects. Day-to-day supervision and mentoring from HDRC Doncaster staff and academic partners builds research identity and practical skills inside operational teams. Because the work happens in real programmes, from analytics and evaluation, to creative and participatory methods, learning cycles straight back into team practice. Each placement leaves a trail of reusable assets, tools, protocols and guidance, catalogued so others can find, apply and build on them. This pathway does not end at the placement: interns often move into research and public health roles while staff grow as mentors, bid writers and project managers, creating a sustainable pipeline of practitioner academics for the region.

5

Number of Fellowship Applications

78

Number of Training Events

Illustrations from Doncaster

- **NIHR Undergraduate Internships** - Two internships delivered in 2025 under HDRC Doncaster’s supervision. The interns took different approaches to their work that reflected their own interests and learning goals. One intern progressed into a research based data science role demonstrating genuine skill transfer and career impact; whilst the other is exploring public health opportunities.
- **NIHR Academy SPARC (Short Placement Award for Research Collaboration)** - Sarah Varga. A 9-month SPARC placement with HDRC Doncaster strengthened the clinical public health bridge, with [Sarah Varga's work reviewing and unpicking ethics pathways and highlighting the need for tailored, proportionate research-ethics processes to support research-capacity building in local government](#). Outputs are now featured on the NIHR Research Support Service website and embedded in City of Doncaster Council’s intranet as part of the governance packs.
- **Strengthened analytical capacity with Pathways to Work** - Recruited Alex Bugg (Insight & Evaluation Lead), who regularly attends HDRC Doncaster delivery meetings and draws on the embedded researcher community, proving mutually beneficial for delivery and capability.
- **Hosted LGA Impact graduates** - HDRC Doncaster is recognised as a supportive placement host and has welcomed a third graduate, Ben Singleton, who is currently focusing on knowledge management systems so that assets, templates and dashboards are discoverable and reusable.
- **Developed public health registrars as researchers** - Created opportunities to grow research competencies: Marie Rogerson contributed to the co-created study on vaping and young people; current registrar Becky Woolley is developing qualitative methods through the co-produced evaluation of the commissioned Nourish & Nurture service.

10 extra bids
out of existing projects

embedding
a culture of
mentorship

- **Inclusive internship commitments** - A pledge to host a Black Data Science Internship (Health Data Research UK) in 2026 expands access and adds advanced analytics capacity to the skills bank.
 - **Co-hosted public health research and evaluation posts** - Two posts funded via the Public Health grant and co-supervised by a HDRC Doncaster’s practitioner academics: Patience Gansallo (embedded in Healthy Places; leads the Active Travel Partnership evaluation; part of a joint, successful NIHR PHIRST application to evaluate Health Impact Assessments in Spatial Planning) and Amy Lazar (embedded in Healthy Lives; leads food systems research). This model is building research culture across complex, multi partner themes.
 - **NIHR practitioner-academic pipeline** – Carrie Wardle and Joanna Rutter each secured NIHR Doctoral Awards and spend 20% practice time within HDRC Doncaster, circulating methods across authorities and strengthening regional research capacity.
- Beyond individual development, the internships helped HDRC Doncaster refine its processes, creating a repository of HR documentation, planning a bank of small projects for future placements, and embedding a culture of mentorship. These steps lay the groundwork for a sustainable internship model and a pipeline of practitioner-academics who can bridge the gap between research and practice.

Funded by **NIHR** | National Institute for Health and Care Research

Continuing the Journey

HDRC Doncaster's work reflects a growing movement to make a plurality of evidence from routine data and evaluation to practitioner insight and lived experience, central to local decision-making. By fostering trust, embedding research into practice, and building capacity across communities and services, HDRC Doncaster are creating conditions for healthier lives and fairer systems. The examples in this report show that change happens when collaboration is intentional and inclusive, when research is not an abstract exercise but a shared tool for solving real challenges. This is just the beginning, and the lessons learned here will continue to shape how Doncaster responds to the wider determinants of health.

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Thank You

Join the conversation: Explore, Share, Reflect

Thank you for reading. The stories in this report, from Women’s Health and youth voice on vaping to whole house retrofit, homelessness systems mapping, gambling harms, and everyday use of dashboards, show what changes when evidence, lived experience and practice move together.

- **Explore:** Revisit a story and try one idea in your own setting (e.g., a rapid evidence brief, a Theory of Change, or an explorable dashboard)
- **Share:** Tell us what you try, pass the materials to a colleague, and spark your own ‘living resource’
- **Reflect:** What counted as “evidence” here? What would count in your service or community, and what support would help you use it?

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